

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

WP7 – Dissemination

This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D 7.3 – 1 st Report on Dissemination Activities			
Work Package	WP 7 - Dissemination			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	01 June 2016	Actual	03 June 2016
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	PLAN02			
Responsible Author	Dr. (Ms.) Machi Simeonidou Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis Ms. Ioanna Pavlou			
Contributions from	Mr. Albert Garcia Macian			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.1	02/04/2016	Draft	Document structure	Mr. Vassileios Tsekeridis
1.0	20/04/2016	Draft	Overview of the deliverable's progress	Dr. (Ms.) Machi Simeonidou, Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou, Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis, Ms. Ioanna Pavlou
2.0	01/06/2016	Draft	Amended after internal review procedure	Mr. Albert Garcia Macian
3.0	03/06/2016	Final	Final comments from partners	Dr. (Ms.) Machi Simeonidou

Disclaimer

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© STEP Consortium, 2015

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	5
2	Dissemination objectives and expected results	5
3	Dissemination reporting procedure	6
4	Dissemination tools prepared until M12	6
4.1	STEP visual identity	7
4.1.1	Colour palette	7
4.1.2	Logo and slogan	7
4.1.3	STEP QR Code.....	8
4.1.4	STEP banners.....	8
4.1.5	Dissemination templates	9
4.2	STEP website	10
4.3	E-mail account	12
4.4	Social media	12
4.4.1	Facebook page	12
4.4.2	Twitter account.....	14
4.4.3	LinkedIn group	15
4.4.4	Google+ page	16
4.4.5	YouTube channel	16
4.5	STEP promotional material	17
4.5.1	Audiovisual material.....	17
4.5.2	Newsletters.....	20
4.5.3	Press releases.....	22
4.5.4	Leaflets and posters	23
4.5.5	Factsheet.....	25
4.5.6	Other printed material.....	25
5	Dissemination activities performed up to M12.....	27
5.1	Network of Interest.....	27
5.2	Press releases.....	28
5.3	Posts in non-project channels.....	28
5.4	Participation in targeted events.....	28
5.5	Project events & person-to-person meetings.....	28
5.6	Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives	29
6	Dissemination impact indicators.....	29

7	Conclusions	31
	ANNEX I – Reporting Templates.....	32
	Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications.....	32
	Template for Reporting Dissemination Events.....	32
	Annex II – Google Analytics Report.....	34
	Annex III – Partners Dissemination Activities.....	38

Table of Figures

Figure 1.	The STEP logo.....	7
Figure 2.	EU emblem.....	7
Figure 3.	STEP project QR code in pink and black font.....	8
Figure 4.	Banner for the STEP Facebook page	8
Figure 5.	Banner for the STEP Twitter account	8
Figure 6.	Banner for the STEP YouTube channel.....	9
Figure 7.	STEP deliverables' template	9
Figure 8.	STEP presentation template.....	10
Figure 9.	STEP website	10
Figure 10.	Disclaimer at the footer of the STEP website.....	11
Figure 11:	STEP Facebook page	13
Figure 12:	Performance of Facebook campaign (April 2016).....	14
Figure 13.	STEP Twitter Account.....	14
Figure 14.	STEP LinkedIn Group	15
Figure 15.	STEP Google + page.....	16
Figure 16:	STEP YouTube channel.....	17
Figure 17:	Screen shot from YouTube.....	18
Figure 18:	Views and watch time per country	18
Figure 19:	Demographics of the STEP video's viewers.....	19
Figure 20:	Traffic sources.....	19
Figure 21.	First page of the 1 st STEP Newsletter	21
Figure 22:	2 nd press release in Spanish and Greek	22
Figure 23.	The first STEP leaflet	23
Figure 24.	STEP poster	24
Figure 25:	STEP Business cards design	25
Figure 26:	STEP post-its design	26
Figure 27:	STEP USB sticks	26
Figure 28:	STEP hats.....	27
Figure 29:	Country of origin of the STEP website's visitors	34
Figure 30:	Acquisition of the STEP website visitors.....	35
Figure 31:	Referral acquisition of the STEP website visitors	36
Figure 32:	Organic acquisition of the STEP website visitors.....	36
Figure 33:	Social acquisition of the STEP website visitors.....	37

1 Executive summary

The dissemination activities in the STEP project are carried out within WP7-Dissemination. The purpose of this deliverable is to report the dissemination activities carried out during the first year of the project, i.e. June 2015 – May 2016. In particular, the objectives and expected results of the STEP project are briefly presented (Chapter 2), while the internal dissemination reporting procedure is described in Chapter 3. The dissemination tools prepared and the dissemination activities performed until M12 (May 2016) are presented in Chapters 4 and 5. Finally, an evaluation of these activities is presented in Chapter 6.

The major dissemination achievements of the STEP consortium for this year are the following:

- The main dissemination material, meaning visual identity, project website, social media accounts, and various promotional printed and electronic material have been prepared and effectively distributed.
- An initial list of members of the STEP Network of Interest has been established and contacted, reaching our target number of 1.000 members by 88%.
- The project partners have attended/ organised several events in which STEP was presented achieving great visibility of the project and preparing the ground for the platform launch and the smooth operation of the pilots.

2 Dissemination objectives and expected results

As it has been defined in deliverable D7.1-Dissemination strategy, the main objectives of the STEP dissemination activities are briefly to:

- Raise awareness of youth all over Europe about the STEP project. Achieve diversity and inclusiveness by involving a demographically balanced group of young people
- Raise awareness of local, regional and national policy makers and public bodies, especially in the field of decision-making on environmental issues
- Maximise participation in operations offered by the developed platform/ mobile app through the project by drawing attention of young people with the use of targeted communication means
- Ensure efficient communication and understanding regarding the project, obtain support and encourage participation of all stakeholders involved, as well as the wide public in disseminating information and exploiting results
- Establish formal and non-formal networks, also strengthening and valorising existing ones, for the exchanging of ideas and practices, in order to develop the sense of a community in participating in decision making in the fields of environment and sustainable development and the public sphere in general.

In the first twelve months of the project implementation, the main focus of the STEP dissemination strategy was to communicate and disseminate the activities of the STEP project, providing an identity to the project and preparing the ground for the next phase, when the platform will be ready and the consortium should engage users in the pilot areas.

The expected results of the STEP dissemination activities are:

- Raising awareness about the project activities, informing the target audiences and the general public about the existence of the STEP project. This will be done mainly during the initial stage of the project and actively supported by the dissemination tools. However, also during the whole lifetime of STEP, the consortium will create publicity of the project to attract potential future stakeholders and ensure maximum impact.
- Informing the target groups about the potential benefits from their use of the STEP platform.
- Achieving active participation of the target groups in the project, e.g. via their attendance in the project workshops and stimulating the participation in the STEP External Expert Advisory Board. The ultimate goal is to achieve the take up of the STEP platform by a significant number of local authorities and young people.

3 Dissemination reporting procedure

In order to effectively track the STEP dissemination achievements, PLANO2 has developed dissemination reporting templates (ANNEX I – Reporting Templates) which all partners have to fill in and send them back to PLANO2 at least every three months. Moreover, project partners are asked to send to the WP7 leader any photocopy, print-out, photo, link, screenshot, etc. relevant to the project if available. Each partner is in charge of locally monitoring its own dissemination activity and reporting the progress and pitfalls to PLANO2, while PLANO2 is responsible for monitoring the feedback and reporting to the project coordinator, DRAXIS.

In compliance with the overall evaluation strategy of the project, a specific ongoing evaluation procedure has been established early in the project so that the impact of the dissemination strategy is measured in all the project phases from its very beginning up to its end. The main issues evaluated are: The quality of the dissemination related tools and activities, and the impact of the dissemination activities on the target groups defined by the project, emphasizing to the impact of the project on young women and special social groups.

In order to monitor the impact of the STEP dissemination activities, quantitative and qualitative indicators are used, according to the characteristics of each activity:

- **Quantitative indicators:** e.g. number of leaflets distributed, number of newsletters publishes, size of audience reached during dissemination activities, number of attendants at project events, website analytics, etc.
- **Qualitative indicators** will be obtained through the implementation of appropriate tools, such as, e.g., satisfaction evaluation questionnaires distributed to participants at events, direct feedback obtained in face-to-face contact with participants.

4 Dissemination tools prepared until M12

The following sections describe the dissemination tools that have been prepared until M12 and that are and will be used throughout the duration of the project. For each dissemination tool the purpose and the status of the tool at the time of reporting are described.

4.1 STEP visual identity

The visual identity aims to provide guidelines that will help all STEP partners to build a strong and consistent branding, messages and visuals for STEP.

4.1.1 Colour palette

It was agreed among partners that the following colour palette will be used for any graphics or colour designs or backgrounds that are used to communicate STEP.

R204 G51 B102	R73 G147 B145	R73 G153 B102
---------------	---------------	---------------

4.1.2 Logo and slogan

The STEP logo plays a central role in the project's visual identity. It aids recollection and recall. The logo should be included in all internal and external communications about the project. Two versions of the logo have been developed: one including the project title and one without it. It is recommended to all project partners not to alter the logo in any way and not to rotate it.

Figure 1. The STEP logo

All the dissemination material of STEP should include the STEP logo, the EU emblem, and a clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The EU emblem is available at the link: <http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/>. The EU emblem accompanied by the abovementioned text will be added as follows:

Figure 2. EU emblem

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493.

Regarding the slogan, although “One STEP closer to participation” was used at the beginning of the project, the STEP partners agreed that it was not catchy enough and it did not communicate the objective of STEP. Thus, a workshop for choosing a project slogan was organised between all partners within the 3rd project meeting in Mollet del Valles. The most popular slogan from the ones proposed was “Deciding together”, and all partners agreed to use this from now on.

4.1.3 STEP QR Code

A QR Code has been created in order to allow mobile users to quickly access the STEP website and download the eParticipation application to their mobile devices when it is developed. The QR code will be included in different types of dissemination material, such as printed leaflets and posters, in order to raise public awareness on the project and increase user engagement.

Figure 3. STEP project QR code in pink and black font

4.1.4 STEP banners

Various online and offline project banners has been created in order to enhance the graphical identity of the project and facilitate the communication of the main ideas of the project. It is envisioned to use these banners on the project's website, newsletters, leaflets, social media accounts, etc. Some of the STEP banners prepared are presented below.

Figure 4. Banner for the STEP Facebook page

Figure 5. Banner for the STEP Twitter account

Figure 6. Banner for the STEP YouTube channel

4.1.5 Dissemination templates

From the early beginning of the project, templates for the preparation of the project deliverables and for the internal and external presentation of information relevant to the project have been prepared. All partners should use these templates for any kind of reports, presentations, press releases and other printed or electronic dissemination material.

Figure 7. STEP deliverables' template

Figure 8. STEP presentation template

4.2 STEP website

A user-friendly, well-designed and easily accessible website has been established and is functioning in its full capacity since M3. The STEP website is available at www.step4youth.eu. It has been designed taking into account specific provisions and requirements related to obligations to the EU, gender issues and target groups/stakeholders, and it is available in English.

Figure 9. STEP website

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

Regarding its structure, the STEP website consists of the public and private section. The public section has been designed for presenting the project activities and progress, making public statements and announcements and disseminating the project deliverables, newsletters, brochure, etc. The website keeps also the target groups informed about the STEP's intermediate and final results. A plug-in has been added in the website's homepage, enabling any interested visitor to subscribe to the STEP newsletter and be kept informed about the project progress. The private section is the Member Area, through which the project partner can exchange, upload and download files for safer data exchange and cooperation. The Member area is limited to consortium partners who have unlimited access to all project related materials, including deliverables and confidential project materials. However, project partners have not decided yet if they will use this member area or if they will continue to use another file-sharing tool to share documents.

In all sections of the website it is clearly stated that the project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, while this disclaimer is accompanied by the EU emblem.

Figure 10. Disclaimer at the footer of the STEP website

The website activity is monitored using the Google Analytics, a tool that tracks and reports visitor traffic and gives a complete picture of the behaviour of the website audience. The following table briefly presents the data analysis for the STEP website's visits. A more detailed analysis is presented in Annex II – Google Analytics Report.

Reporting period	June 2015 – May 2016
Website sessions	1,234
Number of website visits	3,863
Website users	652
Average session duration (period)	4:30
Average percentage of new visitors per month	~51,99%
Average percentage of returning visitors per month	~48,01%

The number of the website visits is quite promising taking into account that the actual activity in the website

is foreseen after the launch of the pilot operations (December 2016 - January 2017). The visits over time indicate that the precise publication scheme that is used pays off. There is a peak in visits when new articles are published. The average duration of a visit shows that visitors are interested in the information published. Moreover, the number of returning visitors indicates that visitors want to follow the progress of the project and return to the website to find the information they seek. On the other hand, the average percentage of new visitors acquired every month (52%) shows that our dissemination campaigns achieve their purpose.

4.3 *E-mail account*

DRAXIS has created an email account for the communication with the public: info@step4youth.eu. This account is included in all used dissemination tools, such as the project website, newsletters, social media accounts, printed material etc. DRAXIS, as the coordinator of the project, is responsible for the administration of this account, while enquiries, comments, and information are forwarded by DRAXIS to project partners if necessary.

4.4 *Social media*

Social media accounts for the STEP project were created in Month 2. PLANO2 is the overall responsible for managing and feeding the general STEP social media accounts. These accounts will be preserved and be constantly fed with posts as they represent an effective way to be in touch with the STEP target groups, and especially young people. The project social media presence will be used primarily as a dissemination channel for the project's news, events and any relevant information.

For the maximum visibility of the STEP social media accounts, direct links from the STEP website to these accounts have been included in each session of the website.

Social media have been used by the consortium to relay the news posted on the website, to share additional information and to tweet on common topics of interest from the very beginning of the project. When posting specific topics any user made sure to clearly mention the project.

Although a respected number of users in social media has been acquired so far, the activity in these accounts is expected to be significantly higher when the platform is ready and the pilot implementations are running. Moreover, for each pilot area at least one dedicated social media account in the language of the pilot partner will be created as soon as the testing phase starts. These accounts will be managed by the corresponding pilot partner.

4.4.1 *Facebook page*

The Facebook page of the STEP project can be found in the following link: <https://goo.gl/49OSG9>. Easy access to the Facebook page is also provided in each section of the project website. Otherwise, the page can be found by searching in Facebook for "STEP H2020 Project".

The official language of the page is English. ROC has created a Facebook page in [Greek](#) where they either share the posts uploaded in the general account or upload posts targeted to residents of Crete. The other pilot partners have also expressed their intention to create a page in their language so that they boost the dissemination of the project's results but also to attract more young people to participate in the STEP pilot implementation in their area.

The STEP Facebook page has been created and is managed by PLANO2, while, as the project evolves, additional administrators may be assigned.

Figure 11: STEP Facebook page

Any information is carefully reviewed before uploaded in the STEP Facebook page, so that it does not include inappropriate or offensive content and it does not contain photos of children. Moreover, all colours and images used abide by the agreed project's visual identity.

The Facebook page activity is monitored using the Facebook Insights which provides information about the page performance, including demographic data about the page audience, and shows how people are discovering and responding to the uploaded posts.

The page is open to everyone to follow. Currently, 335 people like the STEP Facebook page and 105 like the local Greek page. A brief description of the project has been added to the STEP Facebook page in order to inform the general public about the objectives of the project. A link to the STEP website is also provided so that followers can easily access more information on the project.

In order to increase the STEP Facebook visibility and try additional means of dissemination, a Facebook campaign run for three days, from 12th April 2016 until 14th April 2016. The performance of this campaign is very promising as, in only 3 days and with less than €8 spent, it was possible to reach more than 2,000 people and achieve 47 page likes. Thus, the consortium agreed that more social media campaigns will be organised throughout the duration of the project.

Figure 12: Performance of Facebook campaign (April 2016)

4.4.2 Twitter account

The STEP Twitter account is used as a primary tool in spreading the projects’ news and announcements immediately and can be found at the following link: https://twitter.com/STEP_H2020. The name of the STEP Twitter account is “@STEP_H2020”, while the preferred hashtag for the project tweets is “#STEP_H2020”. Tweets are uploaded in a regular base, referring to STEP news and STEP events. The STEP Twitter account is a useful channel to inform and engage with its target audiences.

Figure 13. STEP Twitter Account

Twitter activity is measured through follower users (72 until now).

4.4.3 *LinkedIn group*

A STEP LinkedIn group has been created and is managed by PLANO2. Its name is “STEP H2020 project” and it is available at the following link: <https://goo.gl/m5E6AQ>. As LinkedIn is a business-oriented social networking service, it differs from other social media since it is mostly used for professional reasons. The objectives of using LinkedIn to disseminate relevant to STEP information are listed below:

- To address the target groups of decision makers, professionals, and environmental and youth organisations
- To build a strong network of interested parties in the STEP solution
- To share project-relevant news with people who are in the same arena- giving more credibility to the promotion of the societal and political participation of young people in the decision- making process on environmental issues.

As the STEP LinkedIn group matures throughout the duration of the project, it will be used as a means for spreading news of interest (updates, photos and posts) to group-members. The official language of the group is English. Any LinkedIn member may join this group after the approval of the administrator (Members-only group).

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn group page for "STEP H2020 project". The page header includes the LinkedIn logo and navigation links: "What is LinkedIn?", "Join Today", and "Sign In". The group name "STEP H2020 project" is displayed with a "65 members" count and a yellow "Join" button. Below the group name, there are two main sections: "Group Profile" and "About this Group".

Group Profile: The text describes the project's goal to develop and pilot test a cloud eParticipation platform. It mentions that the platform will be enhanced with web/social media mining, gamification, machine translation, and visualization features. The project aims to promote societal and political participation of young people in decision-making on environmental issues. It also states that five pilots are selected for deployment in Italy, Spain, Greece, and Turkey, involving regional authorities, municipalities, and an association of municipalities. The project will assess usability, effectiveness, and impact, and identify barriers for wide-scale deployment.

About this Group: This section provides key details:

- Created:** June 24, 2015
- Members:** 65
- Owner:** Panagiota Syropoulou
- Managers:** Stavros Tekes
- Website:** <http://www.step4youth.eu>

At the bottom of the page, there is a navigation menu with links for "Sign up", "Help Center", "About", "Careers", "Advertising", "Talent Solutions", "Sales Solutions", "Small Business", "Mobile", "Language", "SlideShare", "Online Learning", "LinkedIn Updates", "LinkedIn Influencers", "LinkedIn Jobs", "Directories", "Members", "Jobs", "Pulse", "Companies", "Groups", "Universities", "Titles", and "LinkedIn © 2016". There are also links for "User Agreement", "Privacy Policy", "Community Guidelines", "Cookie Policy", "Copyright Policy", and "Guest Controls".

Figure 14. STEP LinkedIn Group

The account's editorial control belongs to the leader of WP7. However, the project partners have the right to ask for access to the account.

4.4.4 Google+ page

A Google+ page has been established in order to enable a link with the STEP YouTube presence and any further Google tool which will be adopted. A link has been made between the Google+ Page and the STEP website in order to provide more effective search results for those looking for topics relevant to STEP.

It is envisioned that initially YouTube videos will provide the main content for the Google+ page, but this will be extended to additional updates. Automated posting to Google+ from the STEP Twitter account will be investigated as this would provide a simple mechanism for project partners to contribute on this page.

Figure 15. STEP Google + page

The name of the STEP page in Google+ is “Step Horizon2020” and the page can be found in the following link: <https://goo.gl/d6xzJV>

4.4.5 YouTube channel

The creation of audiovisual material for the promotion of the STEP project is of crucial importance as such tools are more attractive to young people. For the STEP project, a YouTube channel has been created with the name “STEP Horizon2020” and is available at <https://goo.gl/Skfgkj>. The audiovisual material uploaded will be updated throughout the duration of the project and will include:

- Promotional video with general project information addressed especially to young people
- Promotional video presenting the STEP platform and its advantages
- Videos from STEP activities, events, meetings, presentations in conferences etc.

Project partners are encouraged to promote the STEP YouTube channel through their websites, their YouTube channels (if available) and other online dissemination tools.

Figure 16: STEP YouTube channel

Video uploads will be managed by the WP7 leader.

4.5 STEP promotional material

4.5.1 Audiovisual material

Until Month 12, a short promotional video has been created for the STEP project in order to maximise its visibility and explain the objectives of the project in a stimulating way. To this end, this video addresses mainly young people and invites them to participate in decision-making procedures that are executed by their local authority on environmental issues. Moreover, this video aims to create positive emotions to viewers and ensure that their voice will be heard through the STEP platform.

As for all the dissemination material, this video was designed according to the visual identity of the project, while the characters used have features which young people are fond of. The STEP video was produced by a professional video production team, and includes state-of-the-art sound effects, voice over and music. The STEP partners, and especially PLANO2 and DRAXIS, were in constant collaboration with the video production team to ensure that the final video would be of high quality and it would clearly explain the project's objectives. Thus, the script used was produced by the STEP consortium and was modified by professionals.

Moreover, the video includes the EU emblem and a text stating that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 programme.

This first promotional video is available in the STEP YouTube channel and can be directly accessed via the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R90AgFkdnJc> or by searching for "STEP Click your environment now".

Figure 17: Screen shot from YouTube

In the following screens, information from the YouTube analytics is briefly presented.

Geography	Watch time (minutes) ↓	Views	Average view duration	Average percentage viewed
Greece	56 (52%)	104 (58%)	0:32	54%
United Kingdom	11 (10%)	16 (8.8%)	0:42	71%
Belgium	8 (7.4%)	15 (8.3%)	0:32	54%
Spain	8 (7.1%)	8 (4.4%)	0:58	97%
Turkey	4 (3.6%)	4 (2.2%)	0:59	99%
Italy	4 (3.3%)	8 (4.4%)	0:27	45%
Czech Republic	3 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	0:36	61%
Germany	3 (2.5%)	6 (3.3%)	0:27	45%
Brazil	2 (1.7%)	1 (0.6%)	1:53	190%
Sweden	2 (1.6%)	2 (1.1%)	0:51	87%
Canada	1 (1.3%)	2 (1.1%)	0:41	69%
Indonesia	1 (1.2%)	2 (1.1%)	0:38	65%
France	1 (1.0%)	2 (1.1%)	0:32	54%
Qatar	1 (0.9%)	1 (0.6%)	0:59	98%
Cambodia	1 (0.9%)	1 (0.6%)	0:59	98%
Romania	1 (0.8%)	1 (0.6%)	0:54	91%
United States	1 (0.8%)	1 (0.6%)	0:52	87%

Figure 18: Views and watch time per country

As it is deduced from the above figure, the majority of the video views comes from the pilot countries, namely Greece, Italy, Spain, and Turkey, while the first country in the ranking is Greece as three project partners are located there (DRAXIS, ROC, and PLANO2). However, all partners will spend extra effort to increase the STEP video visibility in their country.

Figure 19: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers

Regarding the demographics of the STEP video's viewers, 56% of them were men and 44% were women, while the majority of our audience falls to the age group 25-34, which is a part of the target group of the project (e.g. 18-30 year-olds).

Figure 20: Traffic sources

Finally, from the above Figure it can be deduced that the majority of the video’s traffic comes from websites and apps that have embed the video or its link (70%), while other sources of traffic are the direct URL entry, the YouTube search (8%), and views from YouTube’s suggestions (3%).

4.5.2 Newsletters

A newsletter will be issued every six months throughout the duration of the project to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the project news and progress. They will be prepared jointly by all partners under coordination and responsibility of PLANO2.

The first STEP newsletter has been published addressing information relevant to the identity, progress and results of the STEP project achieved until November 2015. This newsletter has been designed on the project’s newsletters template, which follows the STEP project visual identity and clearly identifies the project as being part of an EU-funded programme. A professional emailing solution (Mailchimp) was used to ensure the best delivery performance to the STEP Network of Interest, while all partners disseminated the newsletter via their channels and emails to their professional/ personal contacts.

The first newsletter was published in November 2015 (M6). Due to the fact that the Network of Interest was not established until M6, the first newsletter was distributed via the communication channels of all partners, and then, when the initial Network of Interest was established (M10) it was sent to them via Mailchimp. The topics addressed in this newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP project
- The importance of youth participation in decision-making procedures in environmental issues
- The technology used in STEP
- The reasons for being involved in the STEP project
- A presentation of the STEP consortium and the STEP External Expert Advisory Board
- A brief description of the pilot operations
- Information about the STEP meetings that took place in Thessaloniki and Istanbul
- A brief description of the STEP progress

The following table presents the newsletters’ details.

Delivery Date	29/3/2016
1st STEP Newsletter	
Successful deliveries	887
Opened	347
Clicked	35

The topics that will be addressed by the following STEP newsletters are:

- News from the pilot cases
- Dates, details, comments regarding project related conferences, meetings, events or publications.
- Result of the STEP project

In order to engage as many stakeholders as possible, the STEP partners are encouraged to distribute the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project. Apart from this, interested parties can subscribe to the newsletter on the project’s website.

Figure 21. First page of the 1st STEP Newsletter

4.5.3 Press releases

Two press releases have been published. The first one is focused on “Societal & political engagement of young Europeans in environmental issues” and the second one describes the successful organisation of the project kick-off meeting in Thessaloniki. Two indicative publications of the 2nd press release are presented below.

Valdemoro participa en un proyecto europeo

La iniciativa STEP promueve el compromiso de los jóvenes en cuestiones medioambientales

El Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro ha sido seleccionado para formar parte del proyecto STEP (Steps Towards European Participation), que tiene como propósito fomentar la intervención de los jóvenes europeos en la toma de decisiones sobre cuestiones ambientales, como parte esencial del desarrollo de un futuro sostenible.

Para ello se va a poner en marcha una prueba piloto a través de una plataforma de participación electrónica en la nube en la que el colectivo juvenil y las organizaciones públicas europeas podrán intercambiar ideas y proponer actividades o proyectos así como aportar sugerencias respecto a temas de medio ambiente. Esta experiencia se va a llevar a cabo a lo largo de dos años de forma conjunta en Valdemoro y municipios y administraciones locales y regionales de Italia, Grecia y Turquía. Se prevé que participen más de 8.200 personas.

STEP, compromiso social y político de los jóvenes en cuestiones ambientales, contará con una inversión total de 3.090.00 euros -más de 104.000 euros están destinados a Valdemoro- que serán financiados íntegramente por la Unión Europea. Del desarrollo de esta iniciativa se encargará un consorcio compuesto por doce entidades del ámbito público y privado de Grecia (país coordinador), Alemania, Reino Unido, España, Turquía, Italia, República Checa y Suecia, entre las que se encuentra el Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro.

La presentación del proyecto STEP, que tiene entre sus objetivos mejorar la confianza de los jóvenes en la Unión Europea e incrementar los canales tradicionales de la democracia representativa, tendrá lugar los días 2 y 3 de junio durante la reunión de los socios del citado consorcio que se celebrará en Salónica (Grecia). ■

«Ευρωπαϊκό έργο STEP: Πραγματοποιήθηκε η εναρκτήρια συνάντηση των εταιρών στην Θεσσαλονίκη»

Προγράμματα Επιχειρηματικότητας Παρασκευή, 05 Ιουνίου 2015 11:56

f
t
e
+
0

Πραγματοποιήθηκε με επιτυχία η εναρκτήρια συνάντηση των εταιρών του Ευρωπαϊκού έργου STEP στις 2 και 3 Ιουνίου 2015 στην Θεσσαλονίκη. Η εταιρεία DRAXIS Περιβαλλοντική Α.Ε., ως συντονιστής του έργου, διοργάνωσε τη συνάντηση αυτή με στόχο την οργάνωση των εργασιών του έργου, ενώ οι εταιρείς είχαν επίσης την ευκαιρία να ανταλλάξουν απόψεις σχετικά με την υλοποίηση των επιμέρους δράσεων.

Figure 22: 2nd press release in Spanish and Greek

Further press releases will be issued whenever important project milestones are reached. They will include important information such as the purpose of the project, milestones reached and results achieved so far. They will target the local or national press in the partners’ countries and will describe the goals of the project in a simple, jargon free language, while they will highlight the benefits for a specific region/country if needed.

4.5.4 Leaflets and posters

A first version of the STEP leaflet was prepared early in the project (M6). The STEP leaflet is available in a double sided three-folded A4 paper providing an overview of the project in an attractive layout. The leaflet was prepared in English by PLANO2 with the agreement of all partners on its content and can be found at the following link: <http://goo.gl/m4NsE2>. The STEP pilot partners have translated the leaflet in their language (Italian, Spanish, Catalan, Greek, Turkish) and distributed it to the pilot sites in order to maximise engagement. Furthermore, partner LINGUATEC translated the leaflet in German in order to distribute it to the “[Global Event for Digital Business- CeBit 2016](#)” and other forthcoming events that will be held in Germany.

Figure 23. The first STEP leaflet

However, from the feedback received from the pilot partners and the audience reached, the need to prepare a second project leaflet that better meets the consortium needs emerged. This leaflet will be a smaller one in a double sided A5 paper. It will also be printed in recycled paper so that the environmental aspect of the project is emphasised. The leaflet will be prepared by PLANO2 in collaboration with the pilot partners and YEE until the end of June 2016 (M13), will be printed by each partner who wants to use it, and will be distributed by any relevant dissemination channels until the end of the project and after its completion.

The STEP poster was prepared in English and the language of the pilot partners in M6, was published in the STEP website, and has been used in project meetings, workshops, conferences and other events in which the STEP consortium has participated so far. The proposed dimensions for the poster printing are 85x200cm.

According to the needs and expectations from each dissemination event, the content of the poster will be modified throughout the duration of the project. PLANO2 is responsible for these updates in collaboration with all partners.

Figure 24. STEP poster

4.5.5 Factsheet

This document describes in a concise way the project's outline, its goals, key issues, technical approach and expected achievements and impact. In addition, it contains organisational information of the STEP partners such as contact details and information on the European Commission funding.

The STEP Factsheet is available at the project website: <http://goo.gl/EMrqbG>

4.5.6 Other printed material

As recommended by the pilot partners, further targeted promotional material should be prepared to ensure the maximum dissemination of the project, especially to young people. Indicative material that has been proposed is: business cards, post-its, USB sticks, cloth bags, hats, etc. Each pilot partner is responsible to prepare the design, print and distribute the dissemination material that better meets their own needs, always under the supervision of PLANO2. Any printed STEP dissemination material is aligned with the relevant guidelines of the European Commission, will agree with the graphical identity of the project, and clearly state the EC's support.

So far, STEP business cards, post-its, USB sticks, and hats have been prepared and are about to be appropriately distributed throughout the duration of the project by all project partners.

Figure 25: STEP Business cards design

The STEP business cards are a convenient way for the partners to maximise the visibility of the project in conferences, person-to-person meetings and other events. They are printed on a 700gr paper with a matte varnish. Moreover, if the round design is printed in bigger dimensions, it can be used as a beverage coaster (sous-verre).

Figure 26: STEP post-its design

The STEP post-its are primarily targeted for the young audience which the project partners approach. The recommended dimensions are 6x12cm.

Figure 27: STEP USB sticks

USB sticks with the project logo and the website URL have been prepared by partner YEE under the consultation of PLANO2. They have been produced in wood so that they can be used at events of the organisation as rewards.

Figure 28: STEP hats

The pilot partner HATAY has prepared hats with the logo and slogan of the project, accompanied by the logo of the HATAY Municipality and used them in a STEP project info-day that took place in March 2016 in Hatay.

5 Dissemination activities performed up to M12

The following sections outline the dissemination activities that have been carried out in the period June 2015 – May 2016 (M1- M12).

5.1 Network of Interest

An initial contact list of the members of the STEP Network of Interest has been established, while the methodology of recruitment and the relevant activities carried out so far are described in D7.4-1st Network of Interest (M12). Until now, the Network of Interest contact list contains 887 individual entries (with a target number of 1.000 members until the end of the project). However, the establishment and management of a Network of Interest will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. Throughout the duration of the project, any additional relevant contacts of the project partners will be added to the STEP Network of Interest. Furthermore, the STEP project recognition and the dissemination activities will enlarge our network of contacts, and these will be added to the Network of Interest. Until now member engagement has taken place through a professional mass emailing solution (Mailchimp), while all project newsletters will be sent to the members of the Network of Interest via Mailchimp throughout the whole duration of the project.

5.2 Press releases

As previously mentioned two press releases have been prepared in English and have been translated by the project partners in their language so that their messages are easily understood by the local communities. The media in which these releases have been published are described in detail in Annex III – Partners Dissemination Activities.

5.3 Posts in non-project channels

Posts about news and results of the STEP project has been uploaded to non-project channels such as blogs, LinkedIn and Facebook groups, and EU websites.

Furthermore, PLANO2 posts STEP news in various Facebook pages and LinkedIn groups relevant to e-participation, e-governance, environmental policy making, sustainability, and youth participation. Indicatively, the following LinkedIn groups have been identified:

- Future of Government
- edemocracy professionals group
- Environmental Impact Assessment
- Environmental Health and Safety Professionals
- e-government/e-citizen
- Decision Makers Group
- Policy Making 2.0
- Sustainability Professionals
- Environmental social science.

5.4 Participation in targeted events

A common way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of the STEP partners in targeted events where STEP will be presented. Each partner has reported to PLANO2 regarding the events they have participated in, accompanied with photos and any proof of evidence regarding their participation. Relevant reports and photos from the events have been communicated via the STEP website, social media and mass media. During the events, dissemination material has been distributed to the participants. All partners were encouraged to inform the WP7 leader about relevant European, national and local events where STEP may be presented.

The events in which the STEP partners have participated within the first year of the project operation are presented in Annex III – Partners Dissemination Activities.

5.5 Project events & person-to-person meetings

As the project matures and further results become available, the consortium will organise dissemination events in order to increase youth awareness on the STEP platform and engage further external stakeholders, such as public organisations, NGOs, strategic decision makers, policy makers, think tanks, scholars, public and private administrations etc. Each partner is free to organise local events for the dissemination of the

STEP project in their area under the guidance of PLANO2. The events organised so far are presented in Annex III – Partners Dissemination Activities.

Regarding the one-to-one meetings, some pilot partners have already organised meetings with representatives of the local authorities and the youth population in their area. The respective reports are presented in Annex III – Partners Dissemination Activities.

5.6 Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives

The STEP consortium has identified and reached similar projects and initiatives with the aim of collaborating with them. Through these collaborations, stakeholders have exchanged views and experiences upon topics of common interest, exploited potential synergies, maximised the potential impact for all actors, and guaranteed the long-term sustainability of the project. EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives in STEP's research domains have been communicated, while project dissemination material has been distributed to them.

Specifically, STEP is in contact with the consortia of [Euth](#), [PARTISPACE](#), [CatchEYou](#), [WeGov](#) and [SENSE4US](#) projects, and has exchanged information and cross-referenced the projects in the website. STEP was presented at the First Optimization Workshop of [Euth](#) in Slovenia, and the coordinator of [Euth](#) is a member of the STEP Advisory Board.

6 Dissemination impact indicators

In order to qualify and evaluate the dissemination actions, STEP has set specific measurable goals. The implementation of the dissemination strategy is regularly evaluated according to the level of realisation of set up dissemination objectives and results. The following table presents the currently achieved values with respect to the aforementioned target ones.

Indicator	Target Value	Currently achieved	Source/ methodology
Number of visits to the project website	45,000	3,863	Google analytics
Number of followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	12,000	587	Accounts' data
Number of women followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	6,000	203	Accounts' data
Number of open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	6	-	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	1,200	-	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

Number of young participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	800	-	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of female participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	600	-	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	12	0	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of young participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	500	-	Participants' lists
Number of female participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	300	-	Participants' lists
Number of non-project events where STEP project will be presented	6	15	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of entries (articles/ press releases) in local, regional and national press (printed and online)	30	16	Copies of the entries
Number of e-newsletters promoted	10	1	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of newsletters recipients	6,000	887	Mailing list record
Number of distributed printed material	4,000	1,526	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of viewers of project related audiovisual material	2,000	181	Number of views through YouTube
Number of stakeholders registered in the STEP network of interest	1,000	887	List of stakeholders
Number of scientific papers published	2	0	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the

			project
--	--	--	---------

7 Conclusions

This Dissemination Report provides the complete overview of the dissemination activities implemented in the scope of the STEP project until Month 12, in accordance with the provisions of the Dissemination Plan issued at the beginning of the project.

The main objective of the dissemination activities of this period was to widely disseminate the vision, concept, objectives and innovation of the project as well as its first results to the commercial and general public communities. From the evaluation of these activities, it is deduced that the performance of the STEP dissemination procedures is quite satisfactory and in accordance with the initial strategy. However, the project partners should pay extra effort in order to reach the dissemination targets, and that is the reason why the 1st dissemination strategy was updated in M12.

ANNEX I – Reporting Templates

This annex includes the reporting templates for: a) dissemination publications, and b) dissemination events. All partners are required to send information on all dissemination publications and events to the WP7 leader using these templates.

Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications

Date	DD/MM/YY
Task	Which dissemination activity does this publication belong to?
Description	Type of publication/ published where/ title of article
Estimated Reach	Number of people the activity has reached
Target Audience	Describe the type of audience this activity has reached
Partners involved	Partner acronym
Results	Did you receive any response? Was the story picked up somewhere else?
Link	If the publication/article is online, please provide a link

Template for Reporting Dissemination Events

Event title, place, dates	Seminar/ infoday/ bilateral meeting/ fair trade/ stand City, Country DD/MM/YY
Event aim & purpose	Write 2-4 lines to describe the objectives of the event and link to the project objectives
Impact to the project	Write 2-4 lines about the impact of such an activity to the project, e.g. create awareness about the project's outcomes, encourage involvement, create synergies with organisations or projects, collaboration agreements with third existing parties, strengthen links with public bodies, consolidate exploitation position, etc.
Type of audience	Write the type of audience that attended the event
Target audience reached	Write the type of audience that you reached during the event
Size of audience	Write the number of all people that attended the event
Coverage Level	Local/ regional/ national/ European level
Partners involved	Partner acronym

Brief report and feedback gathered

- Write 1-2 lines to describe the content and the goal of your presentation/presence
e.g. Content: present project introduction
e.g. Goal: increase public visibility, stakeholders attraction and involvement, etc.
- Write 2 or more lines for any comment you received from the audience that you consider useful and explain how the consortium should utilise this
- Write 1-2 lines about a follow-up / post-meeting you have arranged with any stakeholder

Annex II – Google Analytics Report

This report is useful to get an idea of the behaviour of the visitors of the STEP website, in terms of what browsers they use, what devices they use (desktop, mobile phone, tablet), from which country they are, etc.

Countries of visitors' origin

Country	Acquisition			Behaviour			Conversions	
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate	Goal Completions
	1,234 % of Total: 100.00% (1,234)	52.84% Avg for View: 52.84% (0.00%)	652 % of Total: 100.00% (652)	47.89% Avg for View: 47.89% (0.00%)	3.13 Avg for View: 3.13 (0.00%)	00:04:30 Avg for View: 00:04:30 (0.00%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)	0 % of Total: 0.00% (0)
1. Greece	501 (40.60%)	32.34%	162 (24.85%)	42.91%	3.70	00:07:09	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
2. Spain	167 (13.53%)	68.26%	114 (17.48%)	43.71%	3.63	00:02:58	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
3. Turkey	118 (9.56%)	58.47%	69 (10.58%)	45.76%	2.84	00:02:24	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
4. Belgium	70 (5.67%)	48.57%	34 (5.21%)	44.29%	2.66	00:04:48	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
5. United Kingdom	55 (4.46%)	52.73%	29 (4.45%)	47.27%	2.96	00:03:10	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
6. Czech Republic	48 (3.89%)	35.42%	17 (2.61%)	56.25%	2.29	00:03:01	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
7. Germany	45 (3.65%)	66.67%	30 (4.60%)	48.89%	2.67	00:02:43	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
8. Italy	39 (3.16%)	71.79%	28 (4.29%)	43.59%	2.74	00:02:26	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
9. Brazil	24 (1.94%)	100.00%	24 (3.68%)	100.00%	1.00	00:00:00	0.00%	0 (0.00%)
10. United States	24 (1.94%)	95.83%	23 (3.53%)	83.33%	1.46	00:00:08	0.00%	0 (0.00%)

Figure 29: Country of origin of the STEP website's visitors

The majority of visitors to the STEP website originates from Greece with 40.60% with Spain and Turkey behind, while Sweden does not at all appear in the top 10 countries list. As a recommendation, partner KAIROS should pay extra effort to disseminate the project website in Sweden.

Most Popular Pages

- Partners – 201 views
- Deliverables – 172 views
- Pilots – 161 views
- Dissemination material – 157 views
- Project Description – 151 views

Access media

- Desktop: Of the 1,234 sessions, 1,146 (92,87%) were initiated by desktops. The average number of pages viewed during these sessions was 3.21, while their average duration was 4 minutes and 41 seconds.
- Mobile: 66 visitors were using mobile phones. The average number of pages viewed during these sessions was 1.80, while their average duration was 1 minute and 1 second.

- Tablet: Only 22 people visited the STEP website using their tablet. The average number of pages viewed during these sessions was 3.14, while their average duration was 5 minutes and 25 seconds.

Acquisition Overview

The Direct Acquisition tab shows 660 direct sources used. These direct sources are the landing pages that users land on. This means that the visitor has clicked on a link that was displayed on a search engine that brought them directly to a certain page. The most popular page was the Home page that accounted for 556 sessions to the site. Access to the site from the Members area comes second with 15 sessions. The About Us page is the next popular link with 13 sessions.

Figure 30: Acquisition of the STEP website visitors

Regarding the referral acquisition, website visitors are coming from the websites of the project partners or from webpages of relevant EU projects. The majority of sessions (61) came from the website of partner YEE and visitors spent on average around 2 minutes on the website. Other partners' websites that fall in the top 10 list are the websites of SAMPAS and DRAXIS, while several visitors came from the pages of the relevant-to-STEP projects [Catch Eyou](#) and [PARTISPACE](#).

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

Primary Dimension: Source		Acquisition		Behaviour			Conversions
Source	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate
	247 % of Total: 20.02% (1,234)	57.49% Avg for View: 52.84% (8.81%)	142 % of Total: 21.78% (652)	54.25% Avg for View: 47.89% (13.28%)	2.21 Avg for View: 3.13 (-29.52%)	00:01:59 Avg for View: 00:04:30 (-56.08%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)
1. yeenet.eu	61 (24.70%)	59.02%	36 (25.35%)	42.62%	2.49	00:02:12	0.00%
2. sampas.com.tr	36 (14.57%)	69.44%	25 (17.61%)	36.11%	2.92	00:00:57	0.00%
3. keywords-monitoring-your-success.com	30 (12.15%)	100.00%	30 (21.13%)	100.00%	1.00	00:00:00	0.00%
4. catchyou.eu	25 (10.12%)	40.00%	10 (7.04%)	36.00%	2.48	00:02:44	0.00%
5. partispace.eu	24 (9.72%)	8.33%	2 (1.41%)	54.17%	2.38	00:05:37	0.00%
6. step4youth.us12.list-manage.com	15 (6.07%)	6.67%	1 (0.70%)	60.00%	1.93	00:01:27	0.00%
7. akillikentler.org	13 (5.26%)	84.62%	11 (7.75%)	38.46%	2.46	00:01:36	0.00%
8. atayurtgazetesi.com.tr	9 (3.64%)	88.89%	8 (5.63%)	44.44%	3.11	00:02:32	0.00%
9. step4youth.us12.list-manage1.com	7 (2.83%)	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	85.71%	1.57	00:00:05	0.00%
10. draxis.gr	5 (2.02%)	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	60.00%	1.60	00:05:44	0.00%

Figure 31: Referral acquisition of the STEP website visitors

As for the organic search channel, this is the search engine where users type their queries. For the STEP website, no.1 in the top 10 list is not provided, and this is most likely Google.

Primary Dimension: Keyword		Acquisition		Behaviour			Conversions
Keyword	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate
	185 % of Total: 14.99% (1,234)	57.30% Avg for View: 52.84% (8.44%)	106 % of Total: 16.26% (652)	40.00% Avg for View: 47.89% (-16.48%)	3.68 Avg for View: 3.13 (17.59%)	00:04:33 Avg for View: 00:04:30 (1.19%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)
1. (not provided)	167 (90.27%)	60.48%	101 (95.28%)	40.72%	3.47	00:04:46	0.00%
2. http://www.step4youth.eu/	9 (4.86%)	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	33.33%	6.56	00:03:32	0.00%
3. step4youth	4 (2.16%)	50.00%	2 (1.89%)	0.00%	7.00	00:02:29	0.00%
4. horizon scanning electoral participation	3 (1.62%)	33.33%	1 (0.94%)	66.67%	2.67	00:01:04	0.00%
5. new step video	1 (0.54%)	100.00%	1 (0.94%)	0.00%	5.00	00:00:59	0.00%
6. step4youth.eu	1 (0.54%)	100.00%	1 (0.94%)	100.00%	1.00	00:00:00	0.00%

Figure 32: Organic acquisition of the STEP website visitors

A total of 142 sessions came from social media channels. Facebook accounted for 116 sessions with the average time spent being 7 minutes and 46 seconds and the average page visited 3.67. The bounce rate was 42.24%. Twitter accounted for only 16 sessions and LinkedIn for 10 sessions, while the average time spent was 3 minutes and 2 seconds, and 1 minute and 12 seconds respectively.

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

Acquisition									
Primary Dimension: Social Network Landing Page Other									
Plot Rows Secondary dimension Sort Type: Default									
	Acquisition			Behaviour			Conversions		
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate	Goal Completions	
Social Network	142	33.10%	47	41.55%	3.49	00:06:46	0.00%	0	
	% of Total: 11.51% (1,234)	Avg for View: 52.84% (-37.36%)	% of Total: 7.21% (652)	Avg for View: 47.89% (-13.25%)	Avg for View: 3.13 (11.35%)	Avg for View: 00:04:30 (50.20%)	Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)	% of Total: 0.00% (0)	
1. Facebook	116 (81.69%)	35.34%	41 (87.23%)	42.24%	3.67	00:07:46	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	
2. Twitter	16 (11.27%)	18.75%	3 (6.38%)	37.50%	3.06	00:03:02	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	
3. LinkedIn	10 (7.04%)	30.00%	3 (6.38%)	40.00%	2.00	00:01:12	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	

Show rows: 10 Go to: 1 1-3 of 3

This report was generated on 19/05/2016 at 18:25:01 - Refresh Report

© 2016 Google | Analytics Home | Terms of Service | Privacy Policy | Send Feedback

Figure 33: Social acquisition of the STEP website visitors

Annex III – Partners Dissemination Activities

The STEP dissemination activities carried out until the delivery date of the present document (May 2016) by the project partners are presented in the Table below:

Partner	Type of Activity	Dissemination Activity	URL (if possible)	Reach	Date
YEE	Promotion	Mass media communication (e-newsletter) introducing and presenting the STEP project to the YEE network.	http://goo.gl/uTrz1r	680+	27 February 2015
ROC	Promotion	Posting of the 2nd press release on Greek media. The announcement was made through the site of the Region of Crete and was reproduced by a number of e-newspapers and blogs. It was also published in local newspapers.	Indicatively: http://www.rethnea.gr/article.aspx?id=25773 , http://goo.gl/n6ttV7		4 June 2015
MDV	Promotion	Posting of the 2nd STEP press release on local newspapers (Contrapunt, Mollet a ma, Linia Valles), regional newspapers (El Punt, El 9Nou, Linia Valles), local radio (Radio Mollet), local TV (Valles Visio), regional TV (TV3), and news agencies (Europa Press, EFE, Agencia Catalana de Noticias)			10 June 2015
DRAXIS	Event	Presentation of STEP at the H2020 YOUNG-2014 Projects Policy Kick-off Meeting in Brussels. Networking with relevant initiatives.	http://goo.gl/2qaczc		10-11 June 2015
CSB	Event	Presentation of STEP at the general assembly of the Association of the Municipalities of Locride Area. Several municipalities showed strong interest in the project and many of them have been included in the local plan of pilot testing.		110	18 June 2015
DRAXIS	Promotion	Mass media communication regarding the organisation of the STEP kick-off meeting.	http://www.draxis.gr/news/75		20 June 2015
DRAXIS	Event	Presentation of the STEP project at the First Optimization Workshop of the EUth project (Slovenia).		20+	8-9 September 2015
VLD	Promotion	Presentation of STEP at a meeting with directors of local educational institutions.	http://goo.gl/YrFWJt	38	1 October 2015
ROC	Promotion	Public announcement about the 2nd STEP meeting in Istanbul on local media.	Indicatively: http://goo.gl/YkOlaF , http://goo.gl/Qjbf6G		6 October 2015
YEE	Promotion	Communication of e-newsletter regarding the 2nd STEP project meeting.	http://goo.gl/MJ2VnG	770+	9 October 2015
MDV	Event	Presentation of STEP at the Smart City Expo World Congress in Barcelona. The participating public bodies showed interest in the project and some of them have been included in the STEP NoI.	www.smartcityexpo.com	800+	17-19 November 2015
VLD	Promotion	Press release about the STEP pilot workshop in	http://goo.gl/UxxsI2		19 November

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

		Valdemoro.			2015
ROC	Promotion	Public announcement about the STEP pilot workshop that took place in Valdemoro. Several local and regional media was reached.	Indicatively: http://goo.gl/gqTfJM		22 November 2015
CSB	Promotion	Press conference in the Province of Reggio Calabria. Presentation of the project and stakeholders' attractions in the process. 29 youth leaders has been included in the local plan of pilot testing.		60+	28 December 2015
CSB	Event	Presentation of the project at the regional meeting of the national NGO's network Crescere al Sud. 15 important regional ngos, attending the meeting, showed strong interest in the project.		25	29 December 2015
VLD	Event	Meetings with representatives of other departments of the Municipality. A working group on the project was created.		7	January-April 2016
VLD	Event	Presentation of the project to local teachers and students.		120+	26-27 January 2016
DRAXIS	Event	Person-to-person meetings with representatives of Greek public authorities (Municipality of Thessaloniki, Prefecture of Central Macedonia).		2	February – March 2016
YEE	Promotion	Communication of e-newsletter regarding the 3rdSTEP project meeting.	http://goo.gl/yjlrvr	790+	16 February 2016
HATAY	Promotion	Press releases about the STEP objectives on local media.	Indicatively: http://goo.gl/wneP1N , http://goo.gl/58nTWW , http://goo.gl/Q9fcD4	3000+	22 February 2016
VLD	Event	STEP co-creation workshop in Valdemoro.		6	29 February 2016
VLD	Promotion	Presentation of STEP at the ExpoEducativa exhibition. Information of students and teachers. Synergies were created with some educational institutions of Valdemoro.	http://expoeducativa.jimdo.com/	2500	9-12 March 2016
MDV	Promotion	Promotion of STEP at the Tree Festival 2016 (open-event) in Molle del Valles.		800+	22 March 2016
LINGUA TEC	Event	Promotion at the CeBIT 2016 conference- Distribution of STEP leaflets and newsletter, availability of screens where visitors could navigate in the project website, person-to-person talks	http://www.cebit.de/home		20-24 March 2016
YEE	Event	STEP co-creation workshop in Prague.	http://goo.gl/8XIXsk	7	4 May 2016
YEE	Promotion	Presentation of STEP to youth workers and youth leaders who visited YEE's offices within the international training course "European Citizenship".		15	7 April 2016
MDV	Event	Participation in the Mollet Spring Festival: information stand, leaflets distribution, person-to-person presentation. More than 60 youngsters were informed and some of them want to be active		3000+	10 April 2016

D7.3: 1st Report on Dissemination Activities

		in the forthcoming activities of the project.			
MDV	Event	STEP presentation at the XIX Meeting of Urban Strategic Plans, Zaragoza, Spain. 41 representatives of Spanish public authorities (decision-makers) expressed their interest to be actively involved in the project (Network of Interest)		40+	15 April 2016
MDV	Event	Participation in the Sant Jordi Festival, Mollet del Valles, Spain: information stand, leaflets distribution, person-to-person presentation. More than 90 youngsters were informed and some of them want to be active in the forthcoming activities of the project.		90+	23 April 2016
HATAY	Event	Organisation of a STEP infoday in Hatay, Turkey for local students and public bodies. Mini survey about the audience's impression.		300+	25 April 2016
HATAY	Promotion	Mass media communication about the objectives of the project on local newspapers.		6000+	27 April 2016
YEE	Promotion	Mass media communication about the STEP co-creation workshop organised in Prague.	http://goo.gl/8XIXsk	1000+	6 May 2016

Indicative photos from these dissemination activities are presented below:

